

AGENT-BASED MODELING AND SIMULATION OF VIRUS IN THE HUMAN POPULATION

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Abstract: Prediction of the spread of viruses in the human population is an important agent-based modeling application. This can help in making better policies to protect humanity. By knowing the factors that cause the spread of the virus can alleviate the search and make appropriate handling so that the virus can be reduced even eliminated. Therefore, simulations of the spread of viruses carried out on NetLogo show 2 factors that cause the spread of disease viruses, namely: the possibility of someone being infected with a virus and the opportunity for someone to recover from being infected with a virus. These two things are some of the several factors that cause the spread of the disease virus.

Keywords: Netlogo, Simulation, Virus, Spread Virus, Human Population

INTRODUCTION

The spread of viruses is a non-linear dynamic system that is similar to the spread of epidemics in human populations [1]. Daley et al, (2005) state that infectious disease modeling is a tool that has been used to study the mechanism of disease transmission, to predict future epidemics and to evaluate strategies for controlling an epidemic. Kermack et al, (1927) created the SIR model to be considered in a population. This model has three parts, namely: Susceptible (S), Infection (I), and Recovered (R). This model is used in epidemiology to count the number of vulnerable, infected, and recovered in the population.

Through simulating the spread of viruses in the human population can make predictions of the spread of disease viruses to a small group of humans, so as to prevent the spread of the virus in a long time. Prevention is done by changing the value of variables that determine the level of spread of the virus.

MODEL DEFINITION

The research theory of the Epidemic Propagation Model (Bailey, 1975) was applied in modeling the spread of viruses in the human population. Among these models is SIR (Susceptible-Infected-Recovered). Model S-I-R is a standard model for the analysis of viral disease infections. There are three statuses in each person in this population, namely:

- Susceptible, this condition makes a person vulnerable to being infected with a virus and easily infected by people around him.
- Infected, this condition is the condition of someone who has experienced pain and can infect the people around him according to the probability of infection.
- Recovered, this condition is the condition of someone who has recovered from their illness.

The NetLogo interface in simulating a model for spreading viruses in human populations is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1 Display of NetLogo interface models the spread of viruses in the human population.

A number of sliders are used to set different parameters, as explained below:

- **number-people:** to determine how many initial population numbers.
- **infectiousness:** gives the possibility of infection to people who are neighbors with people who are infected.
- **chance-recover:** the chance of someone's recovery from being infected with a disease virus.
- **duration:** the length of time someone is infected before they recover or die.

In addition to sliders, several buttons are also included as explained below:

- **setup**: this button for rearranging charts and plots and distributing randomly number-people in view.
- **go**: this button to start the simulation and plotting function.

Selecting a **turtle-shape** is used to control whether people are visualized as a person or as a circle.

There are three monitors to show the percentage of the infected population, the percentage that is immune to the virus, and the number of years that have passed. The plot shows (in each color) the number of people who are vulnerable, infected, and healthy. It also shows the number of individuals in the total population in blue.

SIMULATION AND ANALYSIS

Simulation Parameters: The four important parameters of this model are specified as constants in the program code. The maximum human age is set to 50 years or 2600 weeks, if more then, the person will die. The number of people who can be in the world at one time or called carrying capacity is limited to 300 people. Human immunity lasts for 52 weeks. The birth rate is set at an opportunity of 1 in 100 (1%) to reproduce per tick when carrying-capacity is still lacking.

Simulation is only done until the number of years passed is 50 years. The assumption is that when the first generation of humans runs out with no more people infected with the virus, the regulation of the determinants of the spread of the virus is optimal. So, for the following years it can be said that in this human population no virus has been spread.

Virus Spread: Based on predetermined parameters, the simulation is only done by replacing the infectiousness and chance-recover variables. The initial population is 150 people. The length of time a person is infected with the virus also does not change, which is 20 weeks.

Figure 2 The simulation display with the chance-recover variable value is greater than the infectiousness variable value.

In this first simulation, the chance-recover percentage is set greater than infectiousness. Can be seen in Figure 2. When it has exceeded 50 years, in simulations that have variable ranges of 30%, the spread of the virus still occurs. But in simulations that have variable ranges of 50%, the spread of the virus will be to stop. Here shows if the percentage range of the two variables is more than 50% for the more dominant chance-recover variable, then the spread of the virus will be easier to stop. What about the percentage range of the two variables that are less than 30% for the more dominant chance-recover variables? The spread of the virus can still be stopped, but requires a longer time, as shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3 Display simulation when the spread of the virus can be stopped.

In the second simulation, the percentage of infectiousness is set greater than chance-recover. Can be seen in Figure 4. When it has reached 50 years, in simulations that have a percentage range of 50%, the spread of the virus still occurs. But if the percentage range is increased to 60%, the spread of the virus can be stopped.

Figure 4 The simulation display with the chance-recover variable value is smaller than the infectiousness variable value.

Based on the observation of the two simulation conditions above, it turns out that a way to stop the spread of the virus is not only by setting the chance-recover variable greater than the infectiousness variable. But you can also set the infectiousness variable to be greater than the chance-recover variable, provided that the percentage range must be more than 60%.

If the infectiousness and chance-recover variables are set to the same size, the result will be like Figure 5.

Figure 5 Simulation display with the value of the chance-recover variable and the infectiousness variable are the same.

From the results of this simulation, it can be seen that when the value of the infectiousness variable and the chance-recover variable is set arranged in equal numbers the result is the spread of the virus does not occur or stop. But when the value of the infectiousness variable and chance-recover variable is set at 50:50, the spread of the virus will occur continuously.

CONCLUSIONS

The Wilensky Virus Model (1998) found on NetLogo Models Library is used in this simulation to determine the behavior of viruses in the human population. Infectiousness and chance-recover variables are arranged so that the optimal value is obtained to overcome the spread of the virus in the human population. From the analysis of the simulations carried out, it can be concluded that the spread of viruses can be overcome through setting values on the infectiousness and chance-recover variables.

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